

ACTIVE MATTER: A CHANGE IN PERSPECTIVE ON MATERIAL TRANSFORMATION, WITH PAUL KLEE'S *FLORA ON THE ROCK* AS A CASE STUDY

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SUMMARY

This essay reflects on the fragile materiality of Paul Klee's work in the context of "active matter." Through an in-depth examination of *Flora am Felsen* (*Flora on the Rock*), 1940, 343, it explores intrinsic material transformations in the context of durability, museum discourses, and current social issues.

Paul Klee's painting technique, his artistic attitude toward the materials, and his dynamic working process are ad-

dressed alongside the object's layers, their interferences, and the historicity that arises when viewing paintings. The sources analyzed span class notes by Petra Petitpierre, who studied for her master's degree with Klee, and microscopic images of *Flora on the Rock*. The active, transitory quality of the materials and Klee's implied claim to their durability create a tense balancing act.

DYNAMICS IN LIMBO

"The question arises: What are the benefits of technique in a spiritual sense? Then there is the specific question in the sense of chemistry and another in the sense of durability."¹

This quotation comes from the notes of Petra Petitpierre, a master's student who attended Paul Klee's painting class at the Staatliche Kunstakademie in Düsseldorf in 1932. The most recent typescript of her notes, captured in shorthand, is dated July and August 1940 and is held at the Zentrum Paul Klee. The publication by Benteli followed in 1957.²

According to this source, when it came to technique, Klee gave equal weight to the aspects of spirituality, chemistry, and durability. Of primary importance, however, was precision. This high demand for precision, coupled with technical painting

experiments and serial painting methods, led Klee to push the limits of durability, keeping them in limbo. "But precision still plays a major role."³

Klee deemed the experience of failure as a basis for achieving balance between opposite poles. The increased attention to the material and the potential to think about and process it both tangibly and intangibly opens up possibilities for play. Painting technique is "not an unspiritual concept." Rather, it presupposes a "degree of subtlety."⁴ Paul Klee's painting technique implies dynamic processes on various levels. How should we integrate these considerations into the interpretation, presentation, and preservation of these works? These questions must be considered in the context of museums as highly complex centers of cultural production, where different specialists come

together and with missions that continuously respond to evolving social values.⁵

A significant example within the museum context is art transport. The painting *Flora on the Rock*, 1940, 343 (FIG. 1) was transported to nineteen external exhibitions between 1952 and 1987.⁶ In addition to three stations in Switzerland, there were thirteen in Europe and another three overseas. Every year-and-a-half, the painting was subjected to long periods of transport with changes in climate and high levels of mechanical stress. Transport conditions were risky at the time, and protective measures were not yet well developed in the postwar period. This excessive utilization of the painting was responsible for changes observed early on—the wear on the burlap, including processes of stretching and creep, and the resultant low tension; the brittleness of the jute fibers; the cohesion and stress cracks in the paint layer; and the suspected darkening of the colors. After they were classified as damage, the warning calls of the

1970s eventually brought about a turning point: The work has not traveled since 1988. In retrospect, the loan freeze was an effective measure.

Now we stand at another turning point. Our knowledge about the effects of shock impact, acceleration, and climate change on fragile paintings has increased significantly, allowing conservators to reduce risk posed by transportation and display with individually targeted preventative measures. Well-planned transports by courier are now implemented in sustainable collection management strategies, balancing conservation demands and public accessibility.⁷ Their realization—from the crate to the medium of transport, from preparation to monitoring—requires great resources and energy. Concern for the sustainable use of artworks competes with our concern for the environment. Exhibition projects that aim for intercultural exchange in a global context—which always involve movement, travel, and transport—are socially desirable. Yet they are coming under increasing pressure and require new approaches for balanced decision-making processes.

Another relevant question is what we classify as damage. Are changes to a work of art always damage? Of course not. But how should we assess the material transformations from artistic and art historical perspectives while considering the aesthetic aspects of reception and current social discourses? Or, to put it another way, how many micro-cracks can a painting by Paul Klee develop before we see them as damage? How much do we know about the processes of alteration, most of which are not linear? Should we constantly and critically review the scientific data upon which we base our risk models, for example on light protection or the effects of climate fluctuations on the works of art we care for?

Today, these questions have a different tenor and a greater urgency than twenty

Fig. 1
Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [*Flora on the Rock*], 1940, 343, oil and tempera on stretched burlap; original double bar strainer, 90.7 x 70.5 cm, Kunstmuseum Bern
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years ago. Discourses on adequate conservation strategies should remain flexible and incorporate new research topics. The current conception of art conservators and restorers as “agents of change” has led us to take an active role in this conversation.⁸ Our participation is critical to the success of comprehensive and sustainable conservation concepts for works of art in museums.

A CHANGE IN PERSPECTIVE: THE POTENTIAL OF THE “ACTIVITY OF MATERIALS”

Currently, the intrinsic “performativity” of materials is a central topic among international, interdisciplinary research groups dedicated to the subject of “active matter.” The concept encompasses technological innovations, new approaches, and global networks as well as design research on sustainable consumer behavior (circular economy).⁹ Inspired by these initiatives and prospects for the materials of the future, the Bard Graduate Center, New York, launched the interdisciplinary research project *Conserving Active Matter* in 2017. With a multi-perspectival approach, researchers from the disciplines of history, philosophy, conservation, and science as well as researchers and representatives of Indigenous cultures investigated the significance of “active matter” for the preservation of art and cultural artifacts.¹⁰ It seems interesting to me that the connotation has fundamentally shifted away from the study of material degradation as sign of aging, be it desirable or undesirable. Instead, the potential activity of the materials used in artistic production and their intrinsic processes of transformation have come to the fore. This perspective is compelling in relationship to Paul Klee, especially as he oscillated between emphasizing and downplaying materiality.

The research group at the Bard Graduate Center developed a wide range of

questions, including: Does today’s advanced knowledge about dynamic processes at the molecular level in eighteenth-century paintings—i. e. the migration of saturated fatty acid from the paint layer to the surface—influence our understanding of values and the acceptance of material transformation beyond the gain in scientific knowledge? How do we think about and apply the preservation of ephemeral, performative, and virtual materials? What expectations do different cultures have regarding the permanence and temporality of materials? What questions will future “active materials” designed for a sustainable circular economy pose?

When subjected to light and oxygen, materials degrade and lose their strength. In the West, the values attributed to the resultant visual changes are complex and ambiguous. Two important value categories are age value and historical value. Alois Riegl defined the former, first documented in the eighteenth century, as a distinct category in 1903. Emphasizing intangible values that are, nevertheless, perceived through the senses, age value gained relevance in the twentieth century. Historical value, with its focus on the preservation of material relics as historical testimonies and, therefore, the least material change possible, stands in direct opposition to age value.¹¹

In the 1970s, David Lowenthal, then a professor of geography and history at the University of London, debated these conflicting desires and their discrepancy with social expectations regarding the preservation of cultural heritage. A participant in the UNESCO/ICOMOS World Heritage workshop in Bergen and Nara, Lowenthal presented a comprehensive critique of the contemporary understanding of authenticity as early as 1985 in his groundbreaking book, *The Past is a Foreign Country*, which was reissued in 2015. His criticism of UNESCO’s introduction of the principle of “authentici-

ty” into its World Heritage criteria received widespread attention. Lowenthal attached great importance to the interplay between the socially prescribed strategies and policies for cultural preservation and the needs of the communities that identify with that cultural property.¹² This concept has become increasingly important and is reflected in the ICOM’s 2022 definition of museums and in current job descriptions.¹³

The concept of “active matter” has refocused attention on material mutations, but with a different emphasis than in the early 1970s. It calls for an interdisciplinary reconsideration of approaches to preservation that have evolved over time. Furthermore, it invites us to integrate the potential of intrinsic material transformations into art historical and cultural discourses as well as to further explore the properties of historical and new materials.

FLORA ON THE ROCK

Flora on the Rock, 1940, 343 (FIG. 1), is the last work recorded in Klee’s oeuvre catalog for the year 1940. The vibrant, warm shades, the strong red tones, and the contrasting dull, dark, seemingly cooler areas of color are reminiscent of the variety of shapes and colors found on lichen-covered rocks. The stylized linear elements, some suggesting stems, blossoms, and seed capsules, are characteristic of Klee’s formal language. They also relate to a holistic view of the creative process, which Klee—in keeping with the *Zeitgeist* of the early twentieth century—interpreted as closely intertwined with natural processes of growth in his *Bildnerische Gestaltungslehre (Theory of Pictorial Configuration)*.¹⁴

Klee realized his artistic vision using an unorthodox painting technique that attracted attention early on; he continued to develop and elaborate upon it over the years. In the opening speech for the *Junge Bauhausmaler (Young Bauhaus Painters)* exhibition in Halle in 1928, Ludwig Grote

praised Klee’s innovative approach to the technical aspects of painting:

“From this new, boundless and deep sense of space, the medium and technique of painting are given new purposes and meaning. It was chiefly Paul Klee who made unprecedented discoveries that led to the depths of the soul, where the common root of all art lies. He developed the tensions and vibrations of previously unused painting grounds, new ways to handle the surface, and the most refined pictorial structures. Who before him knew what great spatial depth the fabric of a canvas could have.”¹⁵

According to Grote, Klee gave painting technique a new purpose and meaning. The superimposed pictorial supports create a spatial experience and pose a riddle as to how they could have been created. They invite contemplation over a long period of time, continually surprising us. Petra Petitpierre’s notes reveal that Paul Klee also commented on this matter: “If you imagine a painting as a possession that you live with—not just an exhibition object—then it is good if the viewer is given a certain amount of difficulty when viewing it receptively.”¹⁶

In terms of painting technique, *Flora on the Rock* is not a particularly complex work. Here, Klee demonstrates the “sense of space” Grote mentioned and the “tensions and vibrations” of the pictorial support by creating three overlapping spatial layers between the picture support and the paint layer: the fabric itself, the dark primer with the abraded fibers, and the fibers heightened with paint. The oscillation between these overlapping grids and between the organic-looking stippled and brushed-in areas of color demonstrates the “subtle” repertoire of Klee’s technique during his late period (FIGS. 2–4).

TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS

“[A] play of forces that could become an

Fig. 2
Detail, Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [*Flora on the Rock*], 1940, 343,
© Kunstmuseum Bern, photo: Nathalie Bäschlin
The overlapping grids, created by the texture of the fabric, the sanding of its binding points, and the dry application of paint, suggest a sense of space.

Figs. 3 and 4
Detail, Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [*Flora on the Rock*], 1940, 343
Both details feature organic-looking stippling techniques. The thin layers of paint allow the underlying white paint shine through, which increases their luminosity (detail right and detail bottom left). These passages of color contrast with the halftone effects created by exclusive application of the dry paint to the binding points (detail left).

expression determining the whole.”¹⁷ Technique induces a dynamic element that works through the forces that move through, interact with, and permeate the whole. Following Petra Petitpierre’s teaching notes, Klee’s description of the function of technique within the artistic process could be read this way.

Paul Klee’s painting technique received praise during his lifetime—even from his critics. They recognized the “wonderful combination of colors” and the “graphic and technical finesse” of his paintings.¹⁸ The dynamic nature of the material, the visible changes, and the resulting fragility of Klee’s works did not become a subject of study until the 1970s. During that period, the increasing number of international exhibitions at that time also drew attention to these matters.

Klee made few written statements about the importance he attached to painting technique. His diary entries provide insight into his early work and exper-

iments, his discoveries and setbacks.¹⁹ Other rich sources are Klee’s letters as well as the material and technical entries in his oeuvre catalog.²⁰ His experiments in painting technique are of particular importance. A prime example is the work *Ohne Titel* [*Architektur auf der Bühne*] (Untitled [*Architecture on the Stage*]), 1918, which Klee did not enter in his handwritten oeuvre catalog. On the verso, he described the technique, commenting ten years later, “The durability is better than expected” (FIG. 5). In 2018, the technique was verified using analytical methods. The results correspond to Paul Klee’s statements about the material composition and distribution.²¹

Petra Petitpierre entitled a chapter of her notes *Aus der Malklasse von Paul Klee* (From Paul Klee’s Paintings) “Technisches” (Technical considerations). She documents how Klee conveyed the importance of painting technique in his lessons. Paul Klee did not teach painting technique at the Bauhaus or the Düsseldorf Academy and hardly ever commented on technical issues in his *Bildnerische Gestaltungslehre* (Theory of Pictorial Configuration). Rather, according to Petitpierre, technique was taught in the academy’s workshop.²² In his painting classes, Klee presented his own art and discussed and critiqued a selection of the students’ work with them.

Petitpierre described her notes from the painting class as “excerpts and fragments without systematic order.”²³ Three pages long, the chapter on technical considerations reads as a sequence of the artist’s experiences, advice on, and attitudes about painting technique. We learn that Klee attached great importance to the subject. He emphasized the potential of technique as a starting point for discoveries and the imagination, which can ensure a stimulating and fruitful exchange between the viewer and the work of art over a long period of time. In the case of

A Grund:
 A: alte, steinene
 weitere Töne: (blauer pastose) mit Brunsten und wein geblühen, den gelutet.
B Malerei: B: auf diesen Grund mit Aquaröl- und Temperafarben gemalt, diese
 Temperafarbe ist zum Schluss mit Bismutpulver überzogen.
 Die Haltbarkeit ist besser als erwartet
 (aus dem Jahr 1918)
 1928 Klee

1940	Jahr	Blatt	Titel	Technik	Grund
341	F1		Zweifelder Engel	Schwarze Pastell auf Leinwand	Bismutpulver
2	F2		Büste	"	"
3	F3	0,9	Flora am Felsen	Öltemperatur malerei	Leinwand
4	F4	0,7	dieser Stern leht beugen	Pastell auf Leinwand	Leinwand
5	F5		finstere Boots Fahrt	"	Bismutpulver
6	F6		als ob zwei Blüten	Schwarze Pastell auf Leinwand	Leinwand
7	F7		verzweifelt ruhen	Pastell auf Leinwand	Leinwand
8	F8		hier zu spucken	Schwarze Pastell auf Leinwand	Leinwand
9	F9		allein im Garten	"	"
350	F10		ein Amphibien-Strich	"	"
1	F11		beweglicher Aufbau	Pastellfarben auf Bismutpulver	"
2	F12		festlich	"	"
3	F13		Assiel im Gehege	"	"
4	F14		bal champêtre	"	"
5	F15		ditigell	Schwarze Pastell auf Leinwand	Bismutpulver
6	F16		schnauz man	"	"
7	F17		es wird gebaut	"	"
8	F18		zum abschmecken	"	"
9	F19		Gärtnerrei	"	"
350	F20		Tut Lichter	"	"

coarse, thick threads—and the long fibers protruding from these threads—have a worn ochre tone when unbleached (FIGS. 7 and 8). Hydrolysis and oxidation processes induced by light and acid cause them to become brittle and turn brownish over time. Klee began referring to the burlap picture supports in his oeuvre catalog in 1929. Presumably, the aesthetic and artistic qualities of this fabric made it an appropriate “basic structure.” During the economic crisis of the early 1930s, its low price also increased the appeal of burlap supports. Yet Klee’s use of low-quality paper and burlap, whose limited durability were well-known, extended far beyond this period. The materials were suitable for creating the desired “multiplicity,” and they held the intrinsic active potential to explore the extremes of durability without abandoning it. Osamu Okuda has observed that Paul Klee was unsure about the durability of processes he developed in 1938, in which he combined colored paste with newsprint on burlap. In his oeuvre catalog, he categorized the works in this series as drafts (FIG. 9).²⁵ It seems interesting in this context that Klee coated the burlap and newsprint with thin, only partially opaque coatings. He therefore reduced light-induced changes in color while allowing the structure of the fabric and the symbolic texture of the newsprint to show through.

In *Flora on the Rock*, the textured fabric clearly structures the painted surface. It creates a grid that appears both graphic and spatial, which is then accentuated by the overlying paint. Klee primed the pre-mounted fabric with a greenish-brown color. He mixed the paint himself, primarily from bone black and ochre pigments, to which he added a little oil or oil paint and a protein glue.²⁶ After applying a thin layer of primer and allowing it to dry, Klee rubbed it away. The fabric remains visible, with the coat of greenish color only remaining between the binding points, or

Fig. 5
 Detail, Paul Klee, *Ohne Titel* [Untitled] [Verso of *Architektur auf der Bühne* / *Architecture on Stage*], 1918, paper on nettle cloth, 15 x 32 cm, private collection, Switzerland, on extended loan to the Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive, photo: Patrizia Zeppetella
 Klee wrote that the painting was “[from the year 1918].” He dated the observation “The durability is better than expected” ten years later, in 1928.

Fig. 6
 Paul Klee, *Oeuvre catalog 1940, 341–360* [p. 18], Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive
 Excerpt from Paul Klee’s handwritten oeuvre catalog with the following categories: year and number, genre, title, technique, and support. “3/F3/0.9 0.7/Flora am Felsen/oil and tempera paint, stretched burlap.”

Flora on the Rock, the term basic structure (Grundstruktur)—a fabric, the sieve-like structure of a piece of paper, or a grainy layer of sand—comes to mind. The lighting creates reflections, and the tonality of the overlying paint layer varies depending on the light and the nature of the basic structure. The resultant pictorial effects create a sense of oscillating space and color, which Klee subsumed under the terms “multiplicity, [...] structural.”²⁴

In his handwritten oeuvre catalog, Paul Klee listed the following information for *Flora on the Rock*: “0.9 0.7 oil—and tempera= paint on burlap on stretcher frame; panel” (FIG. 6). The burlap fabric with its

protruding fibers.

LUMINOUS COLORS—INCREASED FRAGILITY

Diary entries, letters, and the collection and analysis of materials in Paul Klee's estate demonstrate that the artist both purchased and made his own artists' materials. He produced paint to suit his needs and developed new techniques for application (FIG. 10).²⁷ According to Petra Petitpierre's notes, Klee did not comment on application techniques or on the use of commercially or self-made paints and binders in his painting class at the Düsseldorf Academy. One page of her booklet "Theoretisches Kolleg Klee / Künstlerischen Gestaltungslehre und Farbenlehre" (Klee's Theoretical Seminar / Theory of Artistic Configuration and Color Theory) from the Bauhaus period in Dessau of 1930–31, which focuses on color, deals with the subject of "pigments" (FIG. 11).²⁸ It also includes a list of pigments and a practical exercise that demonstrates the suitability of pigments to represent pure primary colors. According to the result of the exercise, madder red is very close to pure red and is suitable for use in glazes. This color is documented in numerous works by Klee and in his estate in the synthetic

form of alizarin, which has been known since 1868. It seems that Klee limited practical considerations in his teachings to whether pigments are suitable for representing primary colors and how they can be handled. This stands in contrast to his own highly complex painting technique.

In *Flora on the Rock*, Klee painted the green lines with a brush, dragging and dabbing it, alternating between translucent and opaque coverage. The paint is lean, with an aqueous binder and very little oil. Analyses of microsamples have confirmed that Klee deliberately reduced the binder content to an absolute minimum to realize certain color effects.²⁹ At the same time, Klee consciously accepted that the weak cohesion and resultant low mechanical strength could lead to cracking and poor adhesion to the substrate (FIG. 12). Thanks to his solid technical knowledge, he was able to control and anticipate future "material activity" and to assess the consequences of the increased fragility.

For the bright orange-red areas, Klee dabbed on an intermediate layer of white paint to reflect the bright, translucent color (FIG. 3, 12, and 15). In doing so, he achieved a high degree of luminosity. The intermediate white layer varies in thickness; in some areas, the white covers only the binding points of the textile support, thereby accentuating the fabric grid. For the dark, cloudier areas, he either applied saturated red and violet paint directly onto the dark ground or he mixed in a touch of white to create a cloudy, cool effect. Omitting linear elements, he created open, blurred boundary lines (FIG. 2).

In his handwritten oeuvre catalog, Klee recorded oil and tempera paints for *Flora on the Rock*. His technical painting terminology has been the subject of various research initiatives.³⁰ To summarize, Klee's description usually refers to the primary component; as such, other binder compo-

Abb. 7 (right)

Verso, Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [*Flora on the Rock*], 1940, 343, oil and tempera on stretched burlap; original double bar strainer, 90.7 x 70.5 cm, Kunstmuseum Bern © Kunstmuseum Bern, photo: Nathalie Bäschlin
The stamps indicating the format and company reveal the frame's supplier: Schneider Farbwaren Bern. The format is 90 x 70 cm. The wedges were later replaced. The selvage of the burlap is visible at the top. The warp runs horizontally, the weft vertically. Labels, stamps, and inscriptions refer to early exhibitions, changes of location, and identification numbers.

Fig. 8

Detail, Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [*Flora on the Rock*], 1940, 343
© Kunstmuseum Bern, photo: Nathalie Bäschlin
The enlargement clearly shows the varying thickness and density of the burlap. Individual fibers protrude from the loosely spun threads. Vertical thickenings indicate where new weft fibers were woven in. At areas with low weave density, the dark ground shows through.

Fig. 9
Paul Klee, *Vorhaben [Intention]*, 1938, 126, colored paste on newspaper on stretched burlap, original frame, 75.5 x 112.3 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive
The newsprint is clearly visible in the light-colored areas surrounding the dark characters, as the dark lettering shows through the light, thinly applied colored paste. Along the transitions to the black characters, the browned newsprint is visible at times, creating a fine borderline. The color changed quickly, which was Klee's intention. The browning of the paper, the overlapping lines, the printed lettering, and the lively strokes of colored paste create exciting graphic and spatial overlays.

Fig. 10
Painting utensils and materials from Paul Klee's studio [detail], arranged for the exhibition *Paul Klee: Life, Work, and Responses*, Bern, September 19, 2009–May 24, 2010, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, donation of the Klee family and the Bürgi family © Zentrum Paul Klee, Image Archive
The abundance of colorants and binders; the paint in tubes and powder pigments; the handmade pots and paintbrushes; and the shells, palette knives, and brushes convey the great variety of materials Klee used.

sented in *Flora on the Rock*. They were affordable, compatible with binders, and available in a wide variety of shades.³¹

Paul Klee began to acquire his technical knowledge early on through the observation of art and the study of literature. He also conducted technical experiments. An important source, especially for his unorthodox pastel painting technique and the reduction of the binding content, was Wilhelm Ostwald's 1904 publication *Malerbriefe (Letters to a Painter)*.³² At first, it does not seem obvious that Ostwald's technical advice would have remained relevant to Paul Klee into the 1930s. However, art historical research on Paul Klee supports the thesis that he did not develop surprising or independent theoretical ideas. Rather, he carried out select theoretical approaches independently, over a long period of time. Klee remained interested in books he discovered early on—Goethe's *Farbenlehre (Theory of Colors)* as well as volumes on morphology and mysticism—until well into the 1930s.³³

nents cannot be ruled out. It is also important to note that it is unclear whether Klee's descriptions refer to the technique, the material composition, or to both. Oil paint can contain a protein component and be applied like watercolor, i. e. in a translucent manner; tempera paste, tempera, or pastels can also contain a small amount of oil in addition to aqueous components. In *Flora on the Rock*, Klee applied the "fattier" paint with the higher oil content over the leaner tempera paint, in accordance with the rules of painting technique.

We know that Klee was open to modern, synthetic pigments such as alizarin. The more recent toluidine red, Hansa red, and Hansa yellow have also been documented in the estate and analyzed in painting samples. These are among the synthetic pigments introduced in the market. He often used natural mineral earth pigments, which are well repre-

LAYERS OF TIME

As early as 1902, while in Florence during his Italian journey, Klee penned an observation on the perception of color, our visual expectations, and the historicity of material transformation, which he identified both as "destruction" and "beloved patina":

"In the Galleria Antica e Moderna, to see Botticelli's *Primavera*. Of course it surprised me at first, because I had imagined it wrongly, from the point of view of quality as well. Colorlessness partly due to wear. This is what contributes the historic element to a picture and becomes part of it. It is quite a different matter to try to produce new pictures with worn-out colors, like Lenbach. If one loves the patina brought by the centuries, who knows whether one wouldn't reject the pictures in their original state."³⁴

Fig. 13
Paul Klee, *Ohne Titel [Untitled] [Verso of Glas-Fassade / Glass Façade]*, 1940, 288, oil on ground on stretched canvas, 71.3 x 95.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive
The layer of red paint Klee used to cover the underlying composition started flaking off during his lifetime. Klee left it as it was. The stretcher bears the faded inscription “Mädchen stirb und wird” (Girl dies and becomes).

delicate layers of fiber and paint to underline Klee’s categories of “multiplicity [...] structural.” From a conservation viewpoint, we can only agree with Paul Klee: “The durability is better than expected” (FIG. 5).

¹ Petitpierre 1957, p. 16. The author is grateful to Marie Kakinuma and Claudia Bäschlin for numerous helpful suggestions during the preparation of this article as well as to Sarah McGavran for the English translation.

² In the introduction, Petitpierre mentions that the notes were transcribed in shorthand, although these documents are not preserved in her partial estate at the Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern. Petra Petitpierre, *Aus Paul Klee’s Malklassen 1930–1931–1932, Bauhaus Dessau and State Academy of Arts, Düsseldorf*, estate Petra Petitpierre, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, no. 53638, p. 5. Petra Petitpierre’s partial estate at the SIK-ISEA archive in Zurich consists of two manuscripts with handwritten notes and her sketches from Paul Klee’s courses on design and color theory at the Bauhaus in Dessau, HNA 26, 1929–31.

³ Petitpierre 1957, p. 16.

⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 18.

⁵ Domínguez Rubio presented an impressive study of the ways the Museum of Modern Art, New York, functions in the context of museum conservation. See Rubio 2020.

⁶ *Flora am Felsen [Flora on the Rock]*, 1940, 343, oil and tempera on stretched burlap; original double-paneled frame, 90.7 x 70.5 cm.

⁷ Bäschlin et al, 2015.

⁸ Mairesse/ICOM International Council of Museums 2023, p. 97.

⁹ Tibbitts 2017. The book’s cover design brings to life the autonomous transformation of material and its response to information.

¹⁰ Miller/Poh 2022.

¹¹ Riegl 1903; Bäschlin 2020, pp. 109–113.

¹² Cf. Lowenthal 1999, Lowenthal 2015, and Bäschlin 2020, p. 95; cf. also pp. 86–96.

¹³ “A museum is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, conserves, interprets, and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible, and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally, and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection, and knowledge sharing.” ICOM Museum Definition 2022.

¹⁴ See Eggelhöfer 2023.

¹⁵ Unpublished typescript of Ludwig Grote’s lecture for the opening of the exhibition *Junge Bauhausmaler*, Halle, 1928, Archive Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, 4f.

¹⁶ Petitpierre 1957, p. 18.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Vitali 2007, p. 49.

¹⁹ Klee 1988.

²⁰ Klee 1979.

²¹ Zeppetella/Zumbühl/Bäschlin 2019, p. 150.

²² Petra Petitpierre, *Aus Paul Klee’s Malklassen 1930–1931–1932, Bauhaus Dessau and Staatliche Akademie Düsseldorf*, estate Petra Petitpierre, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, no. 53638, p. 63. The typescript contains Petitpierre’s description of how the students primed supports for Klee as a present for his birthday on December 18, 1932. They learned how to do this in the academy’s workshop, which was separate from Klee’s lecture class. This passage was not included in the published version of Petitpierre’s notes.

²³ Petitpierre 1957, p. 5.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 16–18.

Fig. 14
Detail, Paul Klee, *Legende vom Nil* [Legend of the Nile], 1937, 215, pastel, white cotton on stretched burlap, 69.5 x 61.5 cm Hermann and Margrit Ruf Foundation, Kunstmuseum Bern, photo: Nathalie Bäschlin
The ochre paste, visible in places, the jute threads, and the fine cracks from shrinkage create changes in the material and surface structure. Some of these changes stem from the application of the materials while others are due to age.

Fig. 15
Detail, Paul Klee, *Flora am Felsen* [Flora on the Rock], 1940, 343 Kunstmuseum Bern, photo: Nathalie Bäschlin
The cracks and the multitude of small paint flakes indicate the work's fragile condition. Along the fibers, the underlying white layer, which acts as a reflector, is clearly recognizable.

²⁵ Okuda 2008, p. 39.

²⁶ Analysis report by Stefan Zumbühl, Conservation and Restoration Department Archive, Kunstmuseum Bern.

²⁷ Cf. Winkler 2011.

²⁸ Petra Petitpierre, Theoretisches Kolleg Klee, *Künstlerische Gestaltungslehre und Farblehre 1* [Klee's theoretical seminar, Theory of artistic configuration and theory of color 1], HNA 26, 1929–31, Partial estate of Petra Petitpierre at the SIK-ISEA archive, p. 9.

²⁹ Bäschlin/Ilg/Zeppetella 2000; Bäschlin/Zumbühl 2019; Zeppetella/Zumbühl/Bäschlin 2019; Bäschlin 2020, p. 258.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Winkler 2011, pp. 80f.

³² Ostwald 1904, cf. also Bäschlin 2020, pp. 37–43.

³³ Eggelhöfer 2012, pp. 36f., 87f., 104–108;

Wedekind 2014, pp. 92, 93.

³⁴ Paul Klee, Diary entry from April 18, 1902, in: Klee 1988, p. 403. English translation from Klee 1964, p. 108f.

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